

AMIR TEMUR-GREAT STATESMAN AND COMMANDER

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ABSTRACT

This article covers the military art of Amir Temur, the military campaigns under Amir Temur, and to what extent the patriotic feeling of the time was, with great emphasis on the choice of Battlefield.

INTRODUCTION

Amir Temur founded a large state, centered according to his time and times, and in doing so, he incomparably served his people, his land. To realize this, it is enough for Amir Temur to bring before us the existing socio-political situation in the country of the nose, without entering the field of large politics. Emir Temür, who built a powerful Great State, felt well that the economic prosperity of such a state could not be ensured by the military campaigns leading to victories. Recognizing the strategically convenient city of Samarkand as the capital, in the center of movarounnahr, it was believed that this city, located on the Great Silk Road, connecting the Far East with the Muslim world and Europe, should amaze with its majestic structures, lavish palaces, solemn clothes of the people of the palace. In addition, Samarkand has long been a center of Science and enlightenment. Under the Mongols, the city's science and cultural traditions were disrupted. Therefore, the ruler was motivated to achieve his goal above by reviving the same traditions of the city. In all regions of the state of Amir Temur, a clear and fast way of communication was introduced, subject to strict discipline. Without exaggeration, it can be said that such a service led to the development of Amir Temur and the Timurid state of ildam. Traders who came along caravan routes from distant countries brought with them new-new news not only about the goods, but also about the economic situation, lifestyle, habits and religion of other countries¹. Traders who came along caravan routes from distant countries brought with them new-new news not only about their goods, but also about the economic situation, lifestyle, habits and religion of other countries. They were also distributors of culture at the same time, because the manuscript would bring books, paper, tell stories, myths and legends that they heard from other peoples. Any state relies on a certain social group in its activities, while after taking power it protects the goals and interests of that social group. The state of Temur and temur is no exception, of course. He was also, in essence, the state of the owners of property. Timur was a political and skillful

figure. He relied not on one or two classes, but on all classes of the population, in the management of the state and country, unlike the previous rulers. As for the central state system formed by Amir Temur, it was headed by only seven ministers: 1) Minister of the country and the raiyat, 2) Minister of the State, 3) minister of Finance, 4) minister of the administration of dynastic affairs; the fifth, sixth, seventh ministers were ministers of the frontier. But it is not known exactly who and what they are, that is, what tasks are assigned to them. The "tuzuks" say that these three ministers were called ministers of borders and were engaged in affairs related to the subordinate countries. In particular, it is said that "they are the managers of financial transactions and revenues in these lands." May the minister of Balkim have had a panel of three ministers in charge of these affairs under the care of Azam? In the "Zafarnama", the terms Devani adl, Devani quzzot, Devani mansab are found. ADL, the Lord, and quzzot, the Lord, were engaged in the affairs of Justice. So, the fifth Minister was engaged in justice affairs. As for the office, it must be a special devon charged with keeping abreast of any events and incidents at the Royal Court and other lands, monitoring the activities of officials. Such an institution was also in the state of Ghaznavids, Somonians and Khwarezmshahs, and Devani was called mushrif. Obviously, such devon was also in the state of Timur and Timurians, of course. So, the sixth Minister's office stood at the top of the career. It is also known that in the activities of medieval feudal states, (the Emir Temur state is no exception) inter-country trade and ambassadorial relations also played a special role. Amir Temur, counting judges, healers, astrologers and engineers (eighth category) as well as the state backbone, in alliance with doctors and healers, who realized that they would serve the development of their dynastic enterprise incomparably, "he continues," in alliance with patients and healers, I treated. From astrologers, I could determine the days of the planets, their movement and rotation. In alliance with the engineers, I built high buildings and drew the tar-Hin (project) of the garden - U Bostons". The ninth category were engineers (scholars of Hadith) and narrators (historians), and Amir Temur kept this category close to him as well, using great insight and knowledge. The Great emir says of these venerated men, bun-day: "he knew about the stories of prophets and governors, about the Kings that passed before, about how they reached the throne of the kingdom, for what reasons their state found pleasure in them. My experience increased when I heard the stories and messages, work and words of each of the others. I would hear from them what was happening in the universe, and I would be aware of my condition." The legislative system was called a Congress, it passed mainly with the participation of the guides of the large Turkic - mogul tribes, and the supreme ruler was called at any time. The Congress discussed and legislated such issues as war and truce, the election of the supreme ruler. The executive system consisted of devons and other higher government agencies. The executive system of the state brought to life the decisions made by the Congress, the decrees of the king and the daily chores of the state. Amir Temur made military campaigns to Mongolia, Iran, Azerbaijan, Iraq, Shom (Suriya, India, Georgia, Armenia, the Caucasus backlands) between 1371-1404. We are open to the fact that the distant past, the old times come from the legitimacy of socio-economic development, and from the prevailing ideology of those times, there are objective laws of such wars.

The history of military art rightfully recognizes sahibqiron Amir Temur as one of the greatest captains of the world. The military talent of our great-grandfather was vividly

manifested mainly in two directions: as a skillful military organizer and as a valiant commander. The army formed by Amir Temur was extremely disciplined, and the commander muhoraba chogi was able to artistically lead the army units, masterfully send military forces to the places where the fate of the battle would be decided in time, to transcend any obstacles and caves with entrepreneurship, to maintain the combat spirit of the army at the required level. The composition of the troops consisted of soldiers assembled from places such as Movarounnahr, Dashti Kipchak, Khuroson, Iran, Badakhshan, Mongolia, Khwarazm, Mozandaron, Jata. The army was numerically accurate and meticulously organized, its order of battle improved from battle to battle, the army was armed with the most advanced weapons, the parts were distinguished from each other by clothing, flag and tug. It was in command of the Army during the battle. The "Iron traps" state that every eighteen of the regular soldiers were given one tent during the journey. Each warrior had two horses, an arc, a sceptre, a sword, a juvoldiz, a sack, ten nina, a saw, and a leather sack. Every five of Sarah's Warriors are housed in a tent. Each of them was supplied with a helmet, Sceptre, sword, arrow-bow, alms, and the number of horses listed in the order. Only young and skillful Warriors, who knew the secret of military art, had a good command of the direction of retailing the enemy's ranks, acted boldly in difficult times, did not pull a trap from any obstacles, could eliminate in time the chaos that was unlikely to happen in the army, were put in charge by Timurbek. Grandpa sahibqiron pays great attention to the military refinement of his army, introducing high-ranking military titles such as "amir and amirul-umaro", i.e. "chief amir". To talented captains with similar high-ranking titles, he even bestowed the provincial governorship or nobility. Gifts were also set for the Emir, who won the battle by Valor. Whichever Emir defeated an army or conquered a province, he was sired by tug', nog'ora, the rank of bahá'í, the right to enter the councils of state, and the nobility of any sum. It is assumed that each officer is well versed in fighting styles. An ordinary navkar was obliged to strictly fulfill the charter, and in battle he was supposed to be impudent and brave, gentle treatment and fair to the enemy who wanted peace. In terms of tactics, the army of Amir Temur was divided into seven tactical part-forces, intelligence was excellently established, measures were developed for the necessary movement of parts in the battlefield, with a special emphasis on managing them during the battle. The high level of inter-unit communication, the proper selection of military chiefs, had an effective effect on muhoraba's outcome. According to Clavijo's description, timurius ' Army wore an apostolic satin shirt embroidered with gilded thread in peace. It was headed by durus as well as a bead of other precious stones. Two coquils, wrapped in three rows below the neck, were falling on the shoulder. The ambassador makes a special note that the hair braided in this way is the target of the Temurbek soldiers. Before the March, the Sahibqiron arkoni gathered the state, ministers, commanders, admirers, Beks and emirs in a military council — exercise, then a special order was announced for the collection of soldiers, parts were subjected to a military examination. Another of Amir Temur's outstanding contributions to the development of military art is the introduction of the canbul, a cavalry unit designed to protect the wings of the army from enemy attack during the battle and, on the contrary, to bypass the ganyim forces from the side and strike from the back. The Emir Temür army was led by Jahongir Saifuddin and Purhusayn barlos, skilled and brave men who found fame in battles such as

White Buga, Usman Abbas, Muhammad Sultan Qamari, O'rus Buga, Hamza Sulduz, Amir Murizoda, Muhammad Qazghan, yellow Atka and Muzaffar Uch Qaro. In this way, sahibqiron Amir Temur had managed to organize a powerful and most militant army of his time. Such strategic plans as skillful destruction of enemy defenses, shelling of large cities of the ghanims, long-term siege of strong fortresses, strongholds and hisors, encirclement of yov forces as widely as possible, pursuit of an opponent would bring only victory to the Sahibqiran. It is not for nothing that the powerful army created by sahibqiron was recognized as the most advanced army of the world at that time, and later recognized by great commanders, military specialists, served as a lesson and template for several centuries, and was widely studied as a history of military art.

Undoubtedly, for the defenders of our homeland - today's Army, the yawkur of the army troops created by our great-grandfather, the bravado of the bahá'í Warriors-is a true sign. Mental and physical exercises during the reign of Amir Temur the negative assessment that the military campaigns of Amir Temur in former Soviet historiography were all destructive, invasion campaigns in one favor for these military campaigns was not raised condemnation. The historian B.V.Lunin wrote correctly that scholars gave the same assessment of Amir Temur's military campaigns to foreign countries, as evidenced by the lack of in-depth analysis of these campaigns. B. Ahmedov gave a description of the military campaigns of Amir Temur: his reasoning on the reasons for the military march to India, whether it was said to protect Islam, and on the other hand, Iran, Azerbaijan, Iraq, not Tama invasion marches are noteworthy.

To give a worthy assessment of the skill of the military commander of the scientist Amir Temur, the place he held in world history, "it follows the conclusion that it is necessary to carry out a military campaign.English scientist H.In his work "the seven climatic Sultans", the goal of his military campaigns is to carefully study the Great Silk Road, and through it, the efforts of written sources, munshoat (ambassadorial letters)for the development of trade science as well, will help to determine the true causes of the problem. When evaluating military campaigns, it is advisable to analyze the cause and results of these marches.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that in Central Asia, the Timurid state was founded, world history was named after a skillful and talented statesman, and in the East < < < Great Jahangir>> in the West, dozens of works are recorded by a huge number of scholars of the world in centuries moboyrn about the life, social political activity, triumphant military campaigns of Amir Temur, famous Such works were written by arab, Spanish, French, German, Hungarian, Russian and Uzbek historians. In addition Temur fought tirelessly on the path of forming a centralized state in Mavraunnahr, the land of the grandfathers, and Fattah, The Great Army Commander Temür was simultaneously a disaster on the enemies, a hard-handed Monk on his emirs, padari buzrukvor on his ring. If we look at the opposite, Timur was extremely strict in the cause of the prestige, honor, benefit of the state. He did not spare even his own seeds. In state affairs, too, there was a strong, stable and steadfast. From these we can think, because Timur was a supporter of a united, independent, economic and cultural progressive state.

As for his own behavior, he hated Lies, was not deprived of love for knowledge. This is also the reason why there were many poets, poets, scholars, Mystics (Sufi) in his presence, which European historians have cited in their works. From the above, we must say our own personal opinion that Timur was extremely ambitious in doing practical things, and we decided that there was no clear goal for the citizens that could be realized.

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